

Annex to: Scientific opinion on the microbiological safety of ungulates meat intended to be frozen and defrosting of frozen ungulates meat. doi: 10.2903/j.efsa.2026.9825

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Annex B – Time-temperature plots during cooling of bovine, ovine and porcine meat

Figures B.1-B.4 show the additional data on time-temperature cooling profile curves gathered within this opinion, compared to the curves used within the EFSA opinion on transport of meat part 1 (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2014).

Figure B.1. Time-temperature curve for bovine carcasses fitted to data in Klauer (2019), compared with curves developed for the mean (*Tmean*) and worst-case (*Twc*) scenarios within the EFSA opinion on transport of meat part 1 (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2014).

Figure B.2. Core temperatures of ovine carcasses during chilling, used to determine the time to reach 7°C in Baseline I conditions. Temperature measured in deep round (Sheridan, 1990) and Longissimus thoracis (Redmond et al., 2001).

Figure B.3. Observed data and best fit of ovine carcass surface temperature during cooling to two different exponential decay equations. The simple exponential relationship was used for Baseline I conditions. The worst-case scenario (*wc_surface*), developed within the EFSA opinion on transport of meat part 1 (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2014) is included for comparison and is used for Baseline II conditions.

Figure B.4. Observed time-temperature curve for pig carcasses (van der Wal et al., 1995), compared with curves developed for mean (T_{mean}) and worst-case (T_{wc}) conditions within the EFSA opinion on transport of meat part 1 (EFSA BIOHAZ Panel, 2014).

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